

LIMB APRAXIA: WHAT ARE NEUROPSYCHOLOGICAL STUDIES TELLING US ABOUT ITS ROLE IN REAL LIFE?

Veselin Medenica, Lidija Ivanovic
College of Social Work, Belgrade, Serbia

Abstract

Limb apraxia is a neurological disorder characterized by the inability to perform complex movements and gestures despite preserved strength and sensation in the limbs. This disorder occurs due to damage to the brain, usually in the parts responsible for planning and executing movements. Diagnosing limb apraxia is because it can enable early recognition of the neurological disorder, which can enable timely treatment and prevent further worsening of symptoms. It is often emphasized in clinical studies that people with apraxia usually do not have any special implications in their everyday life. There are also studies that claim the opposite. The aim of this review is to investigate these various claims in more detail and establish whether and what implications limb apraxia has for real-life activity.

Keywords: *limb apraxia, daily life, neuropsychology, brain injuries, quality of life*

INTRODUCTION

The praxic activity in humans is the basis for interaction with the external environment, either material or with other people. It is generally considered to occur, as a result of head and brain injuries or after cerebrovascular insults. There is also evidence that limb apraxia can be present in conditions and diseases such as Alzheimer's disease (Cotelli, Manenti, Brambilla & Balconi, 2014; Rapcsak, Crowell, & Rubens, 1989; Stamenova, Roy & Black, 2014), Multiple Sclerosis (Kamm et al., 2012; Rapaić, Medenica, Kozomora & Ivanović, 2014), Parkinson's disease (Foki et al., 2016; Heilman, 2020) and many others (Buchmann et al., 2020).

Given that understanding the problems underlying apraxia is a complex topic that requires knowledge of the anatomical-physiological substrate, the conceptual system and the production system of voluntary motor action, all this complexity has been attracting the interest of scientists, primarily neuropsychologists, for decades. Considering that it is a question of complex systems, science is mostly concerned with simplification through the development of praxic activity and apraxia models. The practical implications of the presence of apraxia have not been studied much because, in a large number of patients, the functions of imitation and the use of real tools are established after some time after the injury (Foundas, et al., 1995).

Models such as Liepmann's, Rothi's, and Roy's (Gonzalez, 1997; Stamenova, Roy, & Black, 2009) have exceptional theoretical importance. Apraxia has been thought to be of theoretical interest, but the implications of apraxia in real life are controversial and have not been fully studied. It is very important to study the real-life implications of apraxia. The role of theory should be to support practice for working with patients. Therefore, it is important to sublimate information about the ways in which apraxia affects a person's real life. It is necessary to find out whether and to what extent theoretical models of apraxia are able to explain the practical implications for a person's life. It is especially important to consider whether and in what way the treatment of limb apraxia can positively affect a person's life.

Objectives

In relation to the above-mentioned, the goal of this paper is to find and sublimate all those neuropsychological studies that indicate the relationship between the presence of limb apraxia and the real life of an individual, including the effects of different types of rehabilitation and treatment.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

For the purposes of writing this review, a search was performed through the KoBSON (Consortium of Serbian Libraries for Coordinated Purchase) service, which provides access to numerous world index databases. Apart from this service, Google Scholar and ResearchGate were also used. The search was performed with the keywords and their combinations: "limb apraxia", "activities of daily living", "quality of life", "implications", "treatment", "rehabilitation", "effects", "real life", "satisfaction", "participation", "social participation", "independence", "disability", "handicap".

The criteria for including papers in the review was that the papers were directly related to the research objective. With a deeper review of the papers by an expert from the field, a triage procedure was carried out according to the specified criteria.

Elements like the dataflow diagram of the PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews were used for reporting on this review (Page, 2021).

RESULTS

With the use of 7 databases and 3 registries, the search found 46 papers that could potentially, according to the content of the title, meet the criteria for including research in the review. Through a deeper analysis of the content of the papers by an expert in the field, it was found that only 12 papers met the above-mentioned criteria and a decision was made to include those 12 papers in the analysis. In the first step, after analyzing the abstracts of the papers, it was determined that 5 papers do not come primarily from the neuropsychological field and that the terminology appearing in them potentially represents a limitation for the interpretation of the results. Of the remaining 41 sources, it was not possible to access 4 of them. A deeper analysis of the content by the expert determined that 25 papers do not meet the defined criteria for inclusion in the study, i.e. only 12 papers are in line with the research objective. The process of selecting papers is shown in Figure 1.

After a deeper analysis of all the papers, the basic information about them is presented in Table 1. Data about the authors, the research participants, the analyzed implications of limb apraxia in real life, as well as about ways of assessing limb apraxia and aspects of real life, such as activities of everyday life, quality of life, etc are presented.

Table 1 Characteristics of included research

Authors	Subjects	Real-life implications	Assessment
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Foundas, A. L (1995)	Unilateral left hemisphere cerebral infarctions	Meal time activities	Apraxia assessment: Gesture to Command subtest of Florida Apraxia Battery (FAB) ADL assessment: Assessment of eating food activity in natural conditions
Kamm et al. (2012)	76 consecutive patients from our MS clinic with the clinically isolated syndrome (CIS), relapsing-remitting multiple sclerosis (RRMS), secondary progressive multiple sclerosis (SPMS), or primary progressive multiple sclerosis (PPMS)	Washing/grooming, dressing, meals and kitchen, everyday tasks, TV/CD/DVD	Apraxia assessment: Test of Upper Limb Apraxia (TULIA) ADL assessment: Sunderland score
Smenia et al. (2006)	41 patients with radiologic (CT) and clinical evidence of left-sided unilateral vascular lesions. Inclusion criteria were the presence of LA (IA or IMA) lasting at least 2 months. Exclusion criteria were a history of previous cerebrovascular attacks or other neurologic disorders, age over 80 years, uncooperativeness, and the presence of orthopaedic or other disabling disorders.	ADL Dependence on caregiver	Apraxia assessment: Before and after treatment, patients underwent oral apraxia, constructional apraxia, IA, IMA, and gesture comprehension tests. ADL assessment: Before and after treatment, a patient's caregiver completed an ADL questionnaire about the degree of assistance required by the patient during the most basic personal care tasks.
Foki et al. (2016).	64 right-handed, early to moderate PD patients 3.44 (1.06)	Buttoning and unbuttoning activities	Apraxia assessment: coin rotation (a surrogate of limb-kinetic apraxia, AST, apraxia screen of the test of upper limb apraxia ADL assessment: buttoning and unbuttoning tasks
Park, J. Kim & M. Kim (2021)	Case study of a 56-year-old man with right frontal, parietal, and corpus callosal infarction	ADL according to Barthel index - personal hygiene, bathing, toileting, dressing, stair climbing, ambulation, and transfer fields	

Aguilar-Ferrándiz et al. (2021)	38 community-dwelling participants with unilateral mild-to-moderate poststroke lesions	ADL according to Barthel index Quality of life	Apraxia assessment: De Renzi tests for ideational and ideomotor apraxia and imitating gestures test, recognition of gestures, test for upper limb apraxia. ADL assessment: Barthel index QoL assessment: Stroke-specific quality of life scale
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DISCUSSION

Limb apraxia and ADL

Foundas et al. (1995) compared patients with unilateral left hemispheric brain damage to a control group with the aim of determining whether patients with the presence of apraxia have greater difficulties in food intake activities than those in the control group. The presence of apraxia was tested by the Florida Apraxia Battery (FAB). The quality of food intake activity was assessed by recording the patients of the experimental and control groups while eating, during lunch in the hospital, after which the data were analyzed. There was a significant positive correlation between the severity of the apraxia in patients and the quality of eating activities in a real-life situation. The authors noticed that patients with left-sided brain injury ate food separately. Only when they were done with vegetables, they would switch to meat, unlike the participants of the control group who took those foods in turn. Also, the participants of the experimental group did not take a drink occasionally during the meal, but most of them drank the entire beverage after taking the meal, in contrast to the participants of the control group.

Kamm et al. (2012) in their research reported that limb apraxia is present in people with multiple sclerosis, but also that limb apraxia is significantly associated with impaired ADLs and manual dexterity in people with multiple sclerosis. Apraxia was assessed by the apraxia screening of TULIA. To evaluate the impact of limb apraxia on ADLs, an adapted version of the Sunderland score was performed. This questionnaire is assessing daily activities (washing/grooming, dressing, meals and kitchen, everyday tasks, TV/CD/DVD). The authors state that apraxia appears to be clinically relevant because apraxic patients had significantly more difficulties in ADLs compared with nonapraxic patients. Basic everyday

tasks such as turning a key in a lock, turning pages of a book, tying up shoe laces, getting food onto a fork, or operating technical devices (personal computer, TV, DVD player) were more difficult for apraxic patients.

Foki et al. (2016) tried to find out the most significant predictors of difficulty in unbuttoning and buttoning in a sample of patients with Parkinson's disease. The assessment found that the coin rotation test, which the authors consider to be a surrogate of limb-kinetic apraxia, is a significant predictor of the performance of the activity of unbuttoning and buttoning.

Treatment of limb apraxia and ADL

Smenia et al. (2006) conducted research that addresses the possibilities of limb apraxia rehabilitation with the aim of improving the quality of performing ADLs in patients with stroke. Patients were tested before and after limb apraxia treatment with apraxia assessment tests and a questionnaire examining ADLs. The research included participants in the control and experimental groups. A total of 41 participants took part in the research. It was found that there was a correlation between performance in the ideational apraxia (IA), ideomotor apraxia (IMA), and gesture comprehension tests on the one hand and the ADL questionnaire on the other. A significant improvement in performance after the apraxia treatment was found in the IA, IMA, and gesture comprehension tests and in the ADL questionnaire. A trend of significant improvement was found in the constructional apraxia test. The authors find that the severity of limb apraxia is associated with dependence on caregiver assistance in the context of ADL. The rehabilitative treatment in patients with limb apraxia after stroke can bring about a significant improvement in ADL functioning. The specificity of the rehabilitation treatment is confirmed by the fact that patients in the control group did not show any change in either the ADL or in limb praxic performance.

Park, J. Kim and M. Kim (2021) presented the positive effects of rehabilitation with the use of virtual reality (VR) through a case study of a 51-year-old right-handed man who presented with sudden weakness of his left side and was diagnosed with right frontal, parietal, and corpus callosal infarction. The primary aim of the research was to indicate the improvement of limb apraxia symptoms that this form of rehabilitation provided, which was confirmed by the authors. The authors did not deal too much with the effects of the VR rehabilitation process on ADL, but in their work, we have found the result of the change in the Barthel index 4 and 12 weeks after the rehabilitation of limb apraxia with the help of VR technology. The Baseline Barthel index was 55/100. Barthel index 4 weeks

after rehabilitation was 84/100, and 12 weeks after rehabilitation 87/100. Improvements were observed in personal hygiene, bathing, toileting, dressing, stair climbing, ambulation, and transfer fields. A limitation of case studies of this type is generally that they cannot take into account the effects of spontaneous recovery, so research under experimental conditions should be conducted to further substantiate these results.

Aguilar-Ferrándiz et al. (2021) conducted a randomized controlled trial to assess the effects of a functional rehabilitation program on apraxia presence, ADLs, and quality of life. The sample consisted of 38 community-dwelling participants with unilateral mild-to-moderate poststroke lesions. Experimental group participants was assigned to an 8-week combined ULA functional rehabilitation program, 3 days per week for 30 minutes. There was a significant difference between all scores on neuropsychological tests between the control and experimental groups after the intervention, however, no difference was found in scores measuring the quality of life and ADL performance. This is one of the few studies in which no relationship between apraxia rehabilitation and QoL and ADL was found. The structure of the rehabilitation program itself should be considered in particular, in order to determine the possible reasons for this result.

CONCLUSION

A review of research addressing the importance of limb apraxia for the real life of an individual found that limb apraxia exudes theoretical importance for further research into the way of performing the voluntary motor activity in humans. The authors unequivocally found an association between the presence of limb apraxia and activities of daily living and quality of life, with some exceptions. Apraxia treatments are confirmed to have a positive effect on ADL performance.

Most researches are to some extent limited by small samples. Assessments of the presence of apraxia, as well as ways of assessing the implications of apraxia in real life, are heterogeneous. Therefore, it is necessary to overcome the mentioned limitations in further research. It is especially important to work on researching the relationship between theoretical models and practical implications. In this way, the value of the model for practice could be demonstrated, and those models that prove to be valuable for practice could become the basis for designing future limb apraxia treatments.

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